
Pyrgopolon regia (Regenhardt, 1961) with ichnospecies
Oichnus paraboloides (Bromley, 1981) from the Late Maastrichtian
'Tuffeau jaunâtre à Thecidea papillata'-bed (Jauche Member)

Nick VAN LIEFFERINGE

TAXONOMY

Kingdom: Animalia

Phylum: Annelida

Class: Polychaeta

Order: Sabellida

Family: Serpulidae

Genus: *Pyrgopolon*

Species: *Pyrgopolon regia*

Author Citation: Regenhardt 1961

GEOLOGICAL TIME SCALE

Eon: Phanerozoic

Era: Mesozoic

Period: Cretaceous

Sub Period: None

Epoch: Late

International Age: Maastrichtian

STRATIGRAPHY

The fossils are associated with a coarse-grained biocalcarenite ("Tuffeau jaunâtre à Thecidea papillata"-bed), part of the (Late Maastrichtian) Jauche Member (**Bless et al.** 1990).

PROVENANCE

Collector: Nick Van Liefferinge (NVL)

Date Collected: 15/02/2026

Acquired by: Field collection

LOCATION

Jauche-la-Marne

Orp-Jauche

Walloon Brabant

Belgium

REFERENCES

Bless M.J.M., Felder P.J. & Jagt J.W.M. 1990: Repeated Tethyan influences in the Early Campanian to Middle Late Maastrichtian successions of Folx-les-Caves and Orp-le-Petit (Eastern Brabant Massif, Belgium), *Annales de la Société Géologique de Belgique*, T. 113 (fascicule 2), pp. 179-197.

Bromley R.G. 1981: Concepts in ichnology illustrated by small round holes in shells, *Acta Geologica Hispanica* 16, 1-2, pp. 55-64.

Regenhardt H. 1961: Serpulidae (Polychaeta sedentaria) aus der Kreide Mitteleuropas, ihre ökologische, taxionomische und stratigraphische Bewertung. *Mitteilungen aus dem Geologischen Staatsinstitut in Hamburg* 30, pp. 5-115.

<Fig. 1>

Fossil specimens I-III of *Pyrgopolon regia* (Regenhardt, 1961) from Orp-Jauché (Walloon Brabant, Belgium). Maastrichtian.

Lateral views and aperture of I (showing a heptagonal cross section).

Specimen III bears a borehole assigned to the ichnospecies *Oichnus paraboloides* (Bromley, 1981).